

Influence of Online Courseware on Students' Individualized Learning Strategies in Rivers State Universities

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the influence of online courseware on Faculty of Education students' individualized learning strategies in Rivers State Universities: counselling implications. The study was carried out in two Rivers State owned universities. The population of the students from selected departments in the faculties were 3000 and 450) students (First year, 2023/2024 season) for Ignatius Ajuru University of Education and Rivers State University respectively. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) sampling table was used to arrive at 342 for Ignatius and 210 for Rivers State University. Quota sampling technique was used to sample the students while, self-developed questionnaire titled influence of online courseware inventory (ICI) and students attitude inventory (SAI) were used for data collection. The questionnaires were given face validation and reliability test and 0.75 index was reached using the Cronbach Alpha Statistic. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions while hypotheses were tested using t-test. The findings revealed that there was influence of online courseware on students' individualized learning strategies and attitudes to lectures. Thus the researchers recommend the improvement of teaching approaches by incorporating the use of online courseware into universities curriculum for the purpose of enhancing students individualized studies, more so, there should be periodic assessment of students' feelings, interest and attitude towards online courseware to enhance adequate deployment of counselling services.

KEYWORDS: online Courseware, Learning Strategies, Attitude, individualized learning, Guidance Counselling

INTRODUCTION

Online courseware is one of the strategies adopted by instructional designers, teachers and instructors to reach learners either as a means of reinforcement on what has been taught in the classroom or as a way of running an entire educational programmes. Online courseware has been invoke for quite a long time especially among distance learners and distance learning institutions, especially within countries with reliable and adequate internet facilities and other equipment that enhances its usage. Presently, in the developing countries like Nigeria, a number of students have started running online certificate courses and engaging in several online learning activities based on the availability of online courseware and the internet. Some of these courseware are Open Educational Resources which makes it free for students to use in other to support their classroom activities or to use it to enhance their learning needs (Mbaba, & Echeonwu, 2023).

The use of courseware is driven by several reasons that include the dynamic nature of education, its development, utilization and the pivotal role of courseware in shaping the learning experiences of students and educators. The dynamism in education and continues evolving nature of technology has presented educators and students with an array of tools and resources that have the potential to revolutionize traditional pedagogical approaches (Gaddi, Entendez, Angob, et al., 2024). Courseware happened to be one of the approaches that were highly used by instructors basically for distant learning and in some cases to support and reinforce the traditional face to face teaching, because of diverse range of digital learning materials, interactive platforms, and instructional content inherent in courseware. The concept of courseware is revealed as a multifaceted learning resource that effortlessly balances educational content and foundational practice of questions within the student's learning path, promoting engagement and compliance to continuous assessment (Schroeder, et al., 2022).

Courseware is the use of electronic platforms to transmit academic and educational resources to users with the purpose of enhancing learning and breaching the challenge of distance and other logistics. It is not just the transmission of educational resources electronically through platforms but the use of instructional designed programmes to enhance individualized learning with access to instructors for questions, interaction with other learners and effective formative and summative evaluations. But to AiniArifah and Norzan, (2008) Courseware can be defined as educational material intended as teaching aids and kits for teachers, usually packaged for use with a computer with the objective to enhance teaching and learning process among students. Patidar, and Singh, (2018) posits that Open Courseware is a type of e-learning model which is delivered via internet and run by the universities or institutions. Open Courseware provide education free of cost to all learners. There is no fee for any type of course. It does not provide any degree or certificate but provides self-learning course material to learners. From the above definitions one can deduced that

online courseware can be used as teaching aids to support teaching process, use as an approach to reinforce learning, especially it is open it is open, it can be use be used as a method of running an entire certificate programme.

Because courseware is multidimensional, there are synchronous, asynchronous and multimedia courseware where multimedia elements are incorporated to expand its effect and viability in teaching and giving room for better interactions. Some research were carried out to test the effect of this tool or approach in teaching and learning. Usser, et al., (2014) studied the effectiveness of interactive multimedia courseware as instructional medium for teaching and find out that there was no significant difference in the performance of pupils in the experimental group and the control group. While, Mbaba, and Umar, (2013) researched on courseware development and its impact on learning in the national open university of Nigeria, the findings revealed high interactivity of students with the courseware. Patidar, and Singh, (2018) also investigated utilizing open courseware amongst students of higher learning institutions in India and the findings concluded that student effectively utilized open courseware in terms of user-flexibility, choice-based access and content delivery. There are other studies that investigated the effectiveness of different courseware including gamification in learning and their findings revealed a positive effect of courseware on students learning and academic performance (Bakan, & Bakan, 2018; Pratama & Setyaningrum, 2018; Hurikrishnan, et al., 2021). As a result teachers and students continue to engage in the use of courseware and other online platforms for learning purposes. In same context, large number of students in developing nations are not able to engage in this modern approach, though most developing countries do have least capability to apply modern practice in education (Ullah, Khan, & Khan, 2017).

Learning strategies varies from one student to another, the strategies also differs from course to course. What then is learning strategies in the context of this study, learning strategies may referred to as systematic and conscious plans, actions or specific action learner uses to tackle a task. These action plan are described as knowing what to do, how to do it, when to do it, and why it is important to do it and in specific manner or pattern. Students use various strategies to maximize the effectiveness of learning and communication. (International, n.d). Individualized learning, instructional strategies are set of techniques adopted by teachers during instructions for the purpose of helping students become independent strategic learners. The strategies so adopted become learning strategies when students select and apply appropriately and effectively these strategies on their own to achieve targets or accomplish tasks (Ukah, et.al 2018; Alberta, & Alberta, 2002). Lots of studies have also investigated the use of this approach and have discovered the need for its use to enhance other approaches adopted by teachers (Lekan, & Emmanuel, 2020).

Specifically, the use of online courseware is most often developed as an approach to run an entire certificate programme. However, some that are planned for open access are used as an open educational resources OER to support students' private studies. Mbaba, and Okwu, (2023) posits that OER can be seen as a piece of information or resources with the following characteristics: digital in nature, distributed with open licenses, modifiable, and supportive of teaching and learning. OER consist of full courses, course materials, modules, textbooks, streaming videos, tests, software and tools. Courseware falls in this two pattern of instructions used in higher institutions open access and restricted courseware. The application of this approach in the universities was enhanced through technology integration in the universities (Huxley, 2014; Mbaba, & Okwu, 2023). But it is not clear if the use of online courseware have an influence on students' learning strategy among students in Rivers state. Despite numerous studies carried out to determine the effectiveness of the instrument among students from various universities which the findings happened to be largely positive with recommendations that support the use of multimedia courseware in learning (Wiana et al., 2018; Setiani, 2022).

It is obvious that students attitude toward a study can help to influence their perceptions and the performance of students in the subjects. Students' attitudes are also affected by the excellence and easiness of using online courseware in relation with students' level and skills in computer (Ullah, et al .,2017; Aixia, 2011). Students' interest, self-esteem and capability in a number of computer skills will also enable students' attitude towards the use of online courseware. Some studies have been done in this direction but it is what investigating hence the growing and expansion of educational programmes is in the direction of online learning and use of courseware. Thus this study seeks to examine the influence of online courseware on library science students' attitude to individualized learning strategy in Rivers State universities in Nigeria.

Research Questions

1. What is the influence of online courseware on students' individualized study?
2. What is the influence of online courseware on male and female students' individualized study?
3. What is the influence of online courseware on students' attitude to lectures?

The following hypotheses were formulated and used to guide the study

1. There is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware between students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru university of Education.
2. There is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware between male and female students' individualized study.

3. There is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware on students' attitudes between Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey design, the population of the study comprises of first year 460 students of 2023/2024 season from the Department of Library Sciences and information Technology, Vocational technical Education and Science Education from Rivers State University, Port Harcourt; and 3000 first year students 2023-2024 season across Department of Library Sciences and information Technology, Vocational technical Education and Science Education from Ignatius Ajeru University of Education, Port Harcourt Rivers state. Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table of sample size was used to a sample of 210 and 342 students from Rivers State University Nkpolu-Oroworokwo, Port Harcourt and Ignatius Ajeru University of Education Rumuolumini, Port Harcourt respectively. Total Sample size is 552 students. Quota sampling technique was used to sample 552 using the questionnaire. The questionnaire was made up four point liket scale titled Influence of Online Courseware Inventory (IOCI) and Students' Attitude Inventory (SAI) developed by the researchers. There were 294 female and 258 male students from the entire sampled students.

The questionnaires were developed with ten items statements each for attitude and influence of online courseware, the questionnaire had four point liket scale of strongly agreed (4), agreed (3), disagree (2) and strongly disagree (1). The questionnaire were given face validation and reliability index yielded 0.75 using the Cronbach Alpha Statistic. This score indicates that the instrument is reliable. Research questions were answered using descriptive statistics while the hypothesis were tested using t-test.

RESULTS

Research questions one: What is the influence of online courseware on students' individualized learning strategies?

Hypothesis One There is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware between students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education.

S/N	Items for influence of online courseware	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
1	Free online courseware support students' private study	157	213	79	103	2.77	1.06
2	Online courseware serves as a source of further information	225	155	109	63	2.98	1.03
3	Online courseware is systematically design with the objectives well stated	137	196	137	82	2.70	1.00
4	Online courseware provides way of assessing my readiness for all examination on each course	167	145	146	94	2.70	1.08
5	Some online courseware give room for feedback	144	139	110	159	2.49	1.16
6	Feedback from online courseware help to remedy deficiencies	155	146	84	167	2.52	1.19
7	Online courseware used by some organization/ field support and promote the study of other field of studies.	98	167	139	148	2.39	1.06
8	Online courseware with hypertext and hypermedia is good in capturing the videos of practical studies	100	185	147	120	2.48	1.02
9	Online courseware is good enable students run other certificate programmes away from what students are studying in the universities.	220	134	71	127	2.81	1.19
10	Online courseware enhanced the classroom interaction, because areas not covered during classroom interactions could be addressed through online courseware.	62	138	165	187	2.14	1.01
Grand mean						2.60	0.57

Institutions	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t-test	Sig	Remark
Rivers State University	210	2.56	0.52	550	-1.298	.195	NS
Ignatius Ajuru University	342	2.62	0.59				

Table 1: Mean ratings and summary of t-test on the influence of online courseware on students' individualized study between Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru university of Education.

The table above shows the mean ratings on the influence of online courseware on students' individualized study. The mean ratings of the respondents of the following items was above the decision mean (Mean 2.50) item 1, 2, 3, 4, 6 and 9 while item 5, 7, 8 and 10. Fall below the decision mean rating. However, the grand mean value of 2.60 clearly indicates that online courseware influences the students' individualized study.

The summary of t-test shows the mean ratings of Rivers State University students as 2.56, SD= 0.52 while the mean ratings of Ignatius Ajuru University 2.62, SD= 0.59. The calculated t-value is -1.298 and significant value of .195 > 0.05 at 550 degrees of freedom. This implies that there is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware between students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru university of Education. Hence, the null hypothesis one is retained at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question Two: What is the influence of online courseware on male and female students' individualized learning strategies?

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware on male and female students' individualized learning strategies.

S/ N	Item for influence	Male, N = 174		Female, N = 178	
		Mean	Std. D	Mean	Std. D
1	Free online courseware support students' private study	2.76	1.08	2.78	1.04
2	Online courseware serves as a source of further information	2.94	1.02	3.02	1.04
3	Online courseware is systematically design with the objectives well stated	2.75	0.99	2.65	1.01
4	Online courseware provides way of assessing my readiness for all examination on each course	2.76	1.07	2.64	1.08
5	Some online courseware give room for feedback	2.44	1.14	2.53	1.18
6	Feedback from online courseware help to remedy deficiencies	2.53	1.18	2.52	1.20
7	Online courseware used by some organization/ field support and promote the study of other field of studies.	2.38	1.07	2.40	1.06

8	Online courseware with hypertext and hypermedia is good in capturing the videos of practical studies	2.40	1.01	2.56	1.03
9	Online courseware is good enable students run other certificate programmes away from what students are studying in the universities.	2.79	1.17	2.83	1.21
10	Online courseware enhanced the classroom interaction, because areas not covered during classroom interactions could be addressed through online courseware.	2.07	0.97	2.20	1.05
Grand mean		2.58	0.57	2.61	0.56

Gender	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	t-test	Sign	Remark
Male	294	2.59	0.57	550	-0.249	0.803	NS
Female	258	2.60	0.56				

Table 2: Mean ratings and summary of t-test result on the influence of online courseware on male and female students’ individualized learning strategies

Table 2 shows the mean ratings on the influence of online courseware on male and female students’ individualized study. The result shows that both male and female students agreed with item 1, 2, 3, 4 and 9 while they disagreed with item 7 and 10. The table reveals a grand mean value of 2.58 for male while grand mean value of 2.61 for the female students. Since the grand mean value for male and female are above 2.50, it is concluded that online courseware influences the male and female students’ individualized learning strategies.

The summary of t-test shows mean ratings of male is 2.59, SD= 0.57 whereas the mean ratings of female is 2.60, SD= 0.56, the t-test calculated value is -0.249 and significant value is 0.803 > 0.05 . Based on this result, it is concluded that there is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware between male and female students’ individualized strategies. Therefore, the null hypothesis two is retained at 0.05 level of significance.

Research Question Three: What is the influence of online courseware on students’ attitude to lectures?

Hypothesis Three: There is no significant influence of online courseware on students’ attitudes to lectures between Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of education, Port Harcourt

S/N	Influence of online courseware on students’ attitude	SA	A	D	SD	Mean	Std. D
1	Create curiosity to study and make contributions, particularly when the instruction is interactive	130	119	146	157	2.40	1.13
2	Online courseware enhanced the desire to acquire more computer programmes for the purpose of improving my skills.	73	96	241	142	2.82	0.96
3	Learning has activities have become more regular than before	0	209	269	74	2.24	0.67
4	My use of computer in doing many other things have been consistent because of continuous engagement in online courseware	120	134	134	164	2.62	1.13
5	I have the drive for study online because of online courseware	207	119	120	106	2.77	1.15
6	The desire for online studies has increased tremendously	154	161	138	99	2.67	1.07
7	Online courseware has motivated me to learn	170	118	133	131	2.59	1.16
8	The use of online courseware has help me to improve my performance in my studies	161	178	155	58	2.80	0.98
9	Mistakes are easily identified corrected before it is too late	152	170	104	126	2.63	1.11
10	Studying through online courseware has increased my self-confidence and autonomy	105	146	118	183	2.31	1.12
Grand mean						2.59	0.45
Institutions	N	Mean	Std. D	Df	T	P	Remark
Rivers State University	210	2.51	0.37	550	-3.094	.002	Significant
Ignatius Ajuru University	342	2.63	0.49				

Table 3: Mean ratings on the influence of online courseware on students’ attitude to lectures

The respondents strongly indicated that ‘Online courseware enhance students’ desire to acquire more computer programmes for the purpose of improving skills’ (mean = 2.82). This was followed by ‘the use of online courseware has help students to improve performance in private studies’ (mean = 2.80). The result also reveals that item 3: Learning has activities have become more regular than before (mean = 2.24) have the lowest mean ratings. The grand mean of the respondents over the rating of the influence of online courseware on students’ attitude to lectures is 2.59 and standard deviation of 0.45. This implies that online courseware influences the students’ attitude to lectures.

The summary of t-test result on the influence of online courseware on students’ attitudes to lectures between Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of education, Port Harcourt. The mean ratings of Rivers State University students is 2.51 and standard deviation is 0.37 while the mean ratings of Ignatius Ajuru University students is 2.63 and standard deviation is 0.49, also, the t-test calculated value is -3.094 and corresponded significant value is $.002 < 0.05$ at 550 degrees of freedom. Hence, the null hypothesis three was rejected at 0.05 level of significance.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

Research question 1 revealed that online courseware influenced students’ individual learning strategies, based on the overall ground mean of ground mail =2.61. The study also answer question 2 which seeks identify the influence on either male or female. Drawing the findings it was concluded that online courseware influence both male and female students individualized learning strategies. The last research question addressed the influenced of online courseware on students’ attitude, it was revealed that online courseware have influenced on students attitude. This study is line the following study of Lekan and Emmanuel, (2020) who studied the effect of corporative and individualized learning strategies on students’ academic retention in Mathematics in Mina metropolis. The both findings agree that online courseware have great influence on attitude of students learning and by extension academic ability and competencies. This also align with the study of Ukah, et al., (2018) who study individualized learning strategies; case study of university of Nigeria Nsukka. Both studies agreed that attitude of students are influenced positive, this can be attributed to the motivation and excitement by way of motivation, interactions and feedback created through the courseware. It is also needful to note that this work have also established that courseware is suitable for individualized learning because of the feature and characteristics of individualized learning strategies embedded (Wiana et al., 2018; Septiana, 2022).

Three hypotheses were tested in this study and the hypotheses are as following: the null hypothesis 1 stated thus, there is no significant influence of online courseware between students of Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru university of Education. The null hypothesis was accepted

revealing that the influence of online courseware from the both schools were consistent. The second hypothesis: there is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware between male and female students' individualized study was retained, meaning online courseware is gender sensitive hence the influence between male and female could not differ. Hypothesis three tested: there is no significant difference in the influence of online courseware on students' attitudes between Rivers State University and Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Port Harcourt. The null hypothesis three was rejected based on the results, this means there is a difference in the attitude of students to learning with the use of online courseware between the two schools. These findings reechoed the findings of Ullah, et al., (2017) whose study investigated Students' attitude towards online learning at tertiary level and came to conclusion that students have no positive attitude regarding online learning at undergraduate, hence their lack of interest in the use of technology in online learning. Moreover, Axiya, (2011) studying the factors influencing learner attitudes toward online learning and development of online learning environment based on the integrated online learning platform, and came to conclusion that students' attitude have serious bearing on interest and performance of students in the deciding to use or not to use. In summary it is clear that online courseware have a way of enhancing attitude and individualized learning. Moreover, the influence of online courseware is cut across the two universities under considerations.

CONCLUSION

The need for flexibility in teaching and learning and the quest for enhancement of individualized learning strategies for better engagement of learners drive this study. Because the use of online courseware have the characteristics and features that addresses individualized learning. Hence, students can study the areas they are interested and interact through the courseware or have the learning done at their convenience. Thus this study give more credence to the use of online courseware based on its influences on students' individualized learning and the consistency recorded from the both universities that was studied. On the basis of the result one can be bold to conclude that technology can enhanced self-paced learning and still provide adequate interaction needed to improve learning. It is also clear from the study that students are engaging online courseware in their personalized studies, especially the open access instructions. This pose the questions on the schools are doing in developing indigenous online courseware that will enable the universities have upper hand in the content their students are using in their studies.

COUNSELLING IMPLICATIONS

Because some online courseware are privately owned, there are issues of quality assurance in respect of the information provided. Thus the counsellors shall among others

1. Guide students on where and how to identify correct information and the type of online software that are suitable for their use
2. Provide effective study tips on how to avoid internet distractions and to be able to more focused on the purpose of their study and
3. Provide other counselling supports for the students in their individualized learning strategies. Counsellors should provide emotional supports especially for students who are struggling to cope in their study and help them to discover personalized or individualized learning strategies in Ignatius Ajuru University of education and Rivers State University, Port Harcourt, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the findings of this study the following recommendations were made:

1. The universities should improve their teaching approach by incorporating the use of online courseware in their curriculum for the purpose of enhancing students individualized studies;
2. For the purpose of assessment and adequate monitoring of students learning activities universities should incorporate home grown courseware activities with feedback mechanism in their online courseware provisions;
3. There should periodic assessment of students' feelings, interest and attitude towards online courseware to enhance adequate deployment of counselling services.

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